

***Xylella fastidiosa* and olive interactions: the key role of the plant cell wall**

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Evidences from the Pierce's Disease suggest a major role of the plant cell wall in the mechanism of pathogenesis. In grapevine, *Xylella* knock-out mutants of Cell Wall Degrading Enzymes - CWDE (polygalacturonase, endoglucanase) are impaired in movement and pathogenicity as they are unable to degrade cell wall middle lamellas of Pit Membranes (PMs), porous selecting structures interconnecting adjacent xylem vessels. In olive, repeated studies comparing the transcriptome profiles of cultivars susceptible (Cellina di Nardò) and resistant (Leccino and FS17) to the *Xylella fastidiosa* (*Xf*) strains "De Donno" (XfDD, subsp *pauca*) and CO33 (XfCO33, subsp *sandyi*) unraveled the involvement of cell wall and plasma membrane-located Receptor-like kinases in the plant response to the infection. Members of the Leucin Rich Repeat Receptor-like kinases (LRR-RLKs) and Wall associated kinases (WAKs) are strongly associated with infections of strains XfDD and XfCO33. Both categories of receptors specifically highlight the cell wall and plasma membrane involvement in the pathogenesis of these two *Xylella* strains in olive, as homologous of LRR-RLKs and WAKs are respectively sensors of the cell wall integrity and involved in the plant immune response and resistance to diverse pathogens in *Arabidopsis thaliana* (At). In addition, At WAK1 respond to oligalacturonide fragments released during the pathogen attack by the CWDE activity, which is consistent with the mechanism of pathogenesis of *Xf*. Further evidences that XfDD exploits the CWDE degradation activity to systemically invade olives came from electron microscope observations of the PMs status in infected plants. Micrographs clearly indicate that the pectic and cellulose structures of the primary walls and of the middle lamellas of PMs interconnecting two adjacent xylem vessels, are highly degraded in XfDD-infected Cellina while these are intact in healthy olives.

Keywords: cell wall, receptors, resistance